

EFFECTIVENESS OF SIMPLE BOOKKEEPING AND RECORD MANAGEMENT AMONG THE PARTNER COMMUNITY OF CABA SUSTAINABILITY EXTENSION PROJECT

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Abstract

The objectives of the extension projects of HEIs is to help alleviate poverty through sustainable livelihood projects extended to the poorest of the poor community, transferring the knowledge and skills through simple bookkeeping and record management, to sustain their micro-small-scale businesses to be their source of income. This study is conducted to determine the level of effectiveness and record management of the mothers-respondents from Barangay Zone 2 as the partner community of the CABA Sustainability Extension Projects. The findings showed that extended knowledge and skills on simple bookkeeping and record management is effective to the partner community in sustaining their micro-small-scale businesses. Hence, the CABA continuously provided seminars-training related to the previously transferred knowledge and skills in realizing the goals and objectives of the CABA sustainability extension project, that is, uplifting the socio-economic status of the poorest of the poor.

Keywords: Sustainability Extension Project, Bookkeeping, Record Management.

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine government continuously provide livelihood activities to the poor and the needy through the action of the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), which actively provides various programs and services for the underprivileged, to the poorest of the poor. Part of these programs is the Sustainable Livelihood Program with the objective of reducing the poverty and inequality by generating employment among poor households and by moving highly vulnerable households into sustainable livelihoods and toward economic stability (World Bank, 2018).

Apart from the goal and objectives of the DSWD programs, the Philippine Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) also contributes to poverty alleviation, not just providing livelihood programs, but also extending the knowledge and skills for sustain their livelihood. This is in accordance with the pertinent provisions of the Republic Act No. 7722 or the Higher Education Act of 1994 for the purpose of promoting or enhancing the Extension function of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), wherein all Philippine HEIs are mandated to conduct Extension Program to help alleviate poverty and provide livelihood to the poorest of the poor.

The College of Accountancy and Business Administration (CABA) of President Ramon Magsaysay State University (PRMSU) in Zambales has initiated an extension program to partner community composed of mostly stay-at-home mothers, of Barangay Zone 2, Iba Zambales. In 2018-2019, the CABA sustainable extension project provided livelihood programs which includes meat processing (pork imbutido) making, salted egg making, and

siomai making. CABA has also extended skills and knowledge in business technology to the partner community such as entrepreneurship, to capacitate them to organize and start their own micro business to make a profit; and simple bookkeeping and record management, to help them keep a complete and accurate record of all financial transactions for decision-making.

This is because, bookkeeping became the underpinning of today’s businesses, whether micro, small, medium, or large. Bookkeeping and record management are the compilation of business-related transactions in a precise and coherent way with the goal that financial condition and business performance can be communicated anytime (Yap, 2019). Bookkeeping is also viewed as an everyday capacity of a business task in tracking inflows and money outflows (Benedict, 2017). Therefore, if the business transactions are recorded properly and accurately, decision-making process would be easy for micro-small-scale business entrepreneurs.

Thus, this study was conducted to determine the level of effectiveness of the extended knowledge and skills on simple bookkeeping and record management to the partner community of the CABA Sustainability Extension Project.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design was employed using a survey questionnaire in gathering the data from the 17 mothers-respondents of the partner community. Frequency and percentage distribution was used to determine the profile variables; mean analysis to determine the level of effectiveness of the simple bookkeeping and record management, with a 4-point Likert scale as based scores, where 4-highly effective as the highest and 1-not effective as the lowest; Analysis of Variance to test the equality of mean to determine if there is a significant variances between the level of effectiveness based on the respondents profile variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to their profile variables.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to their Profile Variables

Profile Variables		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age	28-32 years old	1	5.88
	33-37 years old	5	29.41
	38-42 years old	3	17.65
	43-47 years old	2	11.76
	48-52 years old	1	5.88
	53-57 years old	1	5.88
	58 years old and above	4	23.53
	Total	17	100.00
Highest Educational	Elementary Graduate	1	5.88
	High School Level	4	23.53

Attainment	High School Graduate	6	35.29
	College Level	4	23.53
	College Graduate	2	11.76
	Total	17	100.00
Source of Income	Private Employee	1	5.88
	Government Employee	2	11.76
	Business Owner	14	82.35
	Total	17	100.00
Position in the partner community	President	1	5.88
	Treasurer	1	5.88
	Member	15	88.24
	Total	17	100.00

Age. The majority of the mothers-respondents belonged to the age bracket of 33-37 years old with 5 or 29.41 percent; while the least belonged to the age bracket of 28-32 years old, 48-52 years old, and 53-57 years old, respectively.

Highest Educational Attainment. The majority of the mothers-respondents are high school graduates with 6 or 35.29 percent, while the least is elementary graduate with 1 or 5.88 percent.

Source of Income. The majority of the mothers-respondents started its own business with 14 or 82.35 percent, while the least is a private employee with 1 or 5.88 percent. The business owned by the majority of the respondents was a product of the CABA sustainability extension project, which served as part of their livelihood as source of their income.

Position in the Partner Community. The majority of the mothers-respondents are holding the position of members with 15 or 88.24 percent, while the least are holding the positions of president and treasurer with 1 or 5.88 percent.

Level of Effectiveness of Simple Bookkeeping

Table 2 shows the level of effectiveness of the simple bookkeeping extended to the partner community of the CABA Sustainability Extension Project, to help aid in their micro-small businesses as source of income. It shows that the conducted extension activities on simple bookkeeping is effective with an overall weighted (\bar{x} =2.89). The conducted simple bookkeeping seminar-training-workshop is effective in preparing of daily cash requirement (\bar{x} =3.00); monitoring of expenses, cost of sales, determining the liquidity and solvency, and the need when to secure loans (\bar{x} =2.88); determining the need to increase/reduce the selling price, compares the actual sales/expense with estimates, provides accurate and timely financial reports, and monitors collection of receivables (\bar{x} =2.82); monitoring of payment to suppliers and accounts payable, and determination of profitability (\bar{x} =2.76); monitoring of sales and prepayments (\bar{x} =2.71); and forecasting of cash budget (\bar{x} =2.65).

Table 2: Level of Effectiveness of Simple Bookkeeping

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Monitoring of expenses	2.88	Effective
2. Monitoring of cost of sales	2.88	Effective
3. Monitoring of sales	2.71	Effective
4. Monitoring of payment to suppliers	2.76	Effective
5. Determining the profitability	2.76	Effective
6. Determining the need to increase/reduce selling price	2.82	Effective
7. Comparing of actual sales/expense with estimated sales/expense	2.82	Effective
8. Accurate and timely financial reports in decision making	2.82	Effective
9. Forecasting of cash budget for the next month	2.65	Effective
10. Preparing the daily cash requirement	3.00	Effective
11. Monitoring collection of accounts receivable	2.82	Effective
12. Determining the liquidity and solvency	2.88	Effective
13. Determining the need to secure loans to be used in the operations	2.88	Effective
14. Monitoring prepayments/advance payments	2.71	Effective
15. Monitoring of accounts payables	2.76	Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	2.89	Effective

The simple bookkeeping seminar-training-workshop conducted to the partner community helps them in monitoring and evaluating their financial transactions indicating that proper bookkeeping vital in making decisions to sustain and further expands their businesses.

Level of Effectiveness of Record Management

Table 3 shows the level of effectiveness of the record management extended to the partner community of the CABA Sustainability Extension Project, to help them keep and manage their records in an orderly manner. It shows that the conducted extension activities on record management is effective with an overall weighted (\bar{x} =2.84). The conducted record management seminar is effective in maintaining of records of purchases and other operating expenses, as well as, controlling the generation and growth of records (\bar{x} =3.00); cut costs and saves time and efforts (\bar{x} =2.94); can integrate technologies to record management for record safety (\bar{x} =2.88); summarized the records to improve traceability (\bar{x} =2.65); maintains and updates records (\bar{x} =2.76); and easy retrieval, disposal, and eliminates accidental records destruction (\bar{x} =2.65).

Table 3: Level of Effectiveness of Record Management

Statements	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	Rank
1. Maintained records of purchases and other operating expenses	3.00	Effective	1.5
2. Summarized the records as basis for decision making	2.82	Effective	6.5
3. Maintained and updated the records of cash	2.76	Effective	8
4. Effectively retrieve and dispose records	2.65	Effective	9.5
5. Control the generation and growth of records	3.00	Effective	1.5
6. Assimilate new records management technologies	2.88	Effective	4.5
7. Safeguard important information and documents	2.88	Effective	4.5
8. Cut costs, save time and efforts	2.94	Effective	3
9. Eliminates accidental records destruction	2.65	Effective	9.5
10. Improves traceability	2.82	Effective	6.5
Overall Weighted Mean	2.84	Effective	

The record management seminar conducted to the partner community helps them in maintaining a safe and easy accessible documents needed for decision-making, because it can be costly in their part if records are not managed properly.

Test of Difference on the Level of Effectiveness of Simple Bookkeeping and Record Management according to Respondents' Profile Variables

Table 4 shows the test of significant difference on the level of effectiveness of the simple bookkeeping extended to the partner community based on their profile variables.

The results show that the computed $p=0.695$, $p=0.303$, $p=0.479$, $p=0.954$ are $>$ the 0.05 Alpha Level of significance which indicates that the respondents' level of effectiveness of the simple bookkeeping does not vary in terms of their profile variables.

Table 4: Test of Difference on the Effectiveness of Simple Bookkeeping and Respondent's Profile Variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Age	<i>Between Groups</i>	1.214	6	.202	.644	0.695	Accept Ho Not Significant
	<i>Within Groups</i>	3.140	10	.314			
	<i>Total</i>	4.353	16				
Highest Educational Attainment	<i>Between Groups</i>	1.362	4	.340	1.366	0.303	Accept Ho Not Significant
	<i>Within Groups</i>	2.991	12	.249			
	<i>Total</i>	4.353	16				
Source of Income	<i>Between Groups</i>	.435	2	.217	.777	0.479	Accept Ho Not Significant
	<i>Within Groups</i>	3.919	14	.280			
	<i>Total</i>	4.353	16				
Position in the CABA-Unlad Project	<i>Between Groups</i>	.029	2	.015	.047	0.954	Accept Ho Not Significant
	<i>Within Groups</i>	4.324	14	.309			
	<i>Total</i>	4.353	16				

Significant @ $p \leq 0.05$ Level of Significance

Table 5 shows the test of significant difference on the level of effectiveness of record management extended to the partner community based on their profile variables.

The results show that the computed $p=0.242$, $p=0.613$, $p=0.707$, $p=0.871$ are $>$ the 0.05 Alpha Level of significance which indicates that the respondents' level of effectiveness of the record management does not vary in terms of their profile variables.

Table 5: Test of Difference on the Effectiveness of Record Management and Respondent's Profile Variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Age	<i>Between Groups</i>	1.434	6	.239	1.607	0.242	Accept Ho Not Significant
	<i>Within Groups</i>	1.487	10	.149			
	<i>Total</i>	2.921	16				
Highest Educational Attainment	<i>Between Groups</i>	.546	4	.137	.690	0.613	Accept Ho Not Significant
	<i>Within Groups</i>	2.375	12	.198			
	<i>Total</i>	2.921	16				
Source of Income	<i>Between Groups</i>	.141	2	.071	.355	0.707	Accept Ho Not Significant
	<i>Within Groups</i>	2.780	14	.199			
	<i>Total</i>	2.921	16				
Position in the CABA-Unlad Project	<i>Between Groups</i>	.057	2	.029	.140	0.871	Accept Ho Not Significant
	<i>Within Groups</i>	2.864	14	.205			
	<i>Total</i>	2.921	16				

Significant @ $p \leq 0.05$ Level of Significance

The simple bookkeeping and record management are equally important in monitoring and evaluating business activities for sound decision-making to sustain a business. The extended knowledge and skills was effective to the partner community in sustaining their micro-small-scale businesses. Hence, the CABA continuously provided seminars-training related to the previously transferred knowledge and skills to the partner community in realizing the goals and objectives of the CABA sustainability extension project, that is, uplifting the socio-economic status of the poorest of the poor.

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